

Effect of Substituents on Extent of Hetero-Association In Solution. I. Trifluoroacetic Acid with Benzophenone

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The effect of substituted groups in benzophenone on the extent of its cross-association with trifluoroacetic acid in the non-volatile, non-polar solvent diphenylmethane has been investigated at 35°, utilizing a vapour pressure method described previously². The substituents used were the chloro and the bromo groups, separately, on the para position of one of the phenyl groups of benzophenone. The results show that the presence of either substituent hinders the extent of complex formation between trifluoroacetic acid and benzophenone. The results, also show that the hindrance is greater in the case of the chloro group. The hindrance of the extent of complex formation is attributed mainly to the inductive and resonance effects of the substituents.

THE hetero-association of trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) with benzophenone, in the non-polar, non-volatile solvent diphenylmethane (DPM) was reported before³, and the results were interpreted as due to the formation of non-volatile hydrogen-bonded complexes of 1 : 1 and 2 : 1 TFA to benzophenone, respectively. The hetero-hydrogen bonds were formed between the acidic proton of the very potent proton donor TFA, and the lone pairs of electrons on the basic carbonyl-oxygen of benzophenone. It was reported before also^{3,4}, that TFA itself self-associates in the same solvent, and a monomer-dimer equilibrium exists.

It was felt interesting and informative to investigate the effect of substituents in the oxygen-base benzophenone on the extent of its cross-association with TFA, and to compare the effects of such substituents. The method should prove important, then, in discussing mechanisms, structures and stabilities in the absence and in the presence of substituents, where hetero-hydrogen bonding, in general, is involved.

No attempt was made for lengthy calculations of equilibrium constants, since the study was made on a semi-qualitative basis mainly to investigate the effect of the substituents.

Experimental

Materials :

All the reagents used were either analytical reagents or CP grade reagents. DPM was purified by vacuum distillation. TFA was purified by double distillation through a 30-plate Oldershaw column at a reflux ratio in excess of 10 : 1. Benzophenone, 4-chlorobenzophenone and 4-bromobenzophenone were purified by double crystallization. After purification, all reagents were stored in vacuum desiccators containing an appropriate drying agent.

Apparatus and Technique :

The vapour pressure method employed in this work has been described previously² in detail. It comprises a certain vapour pressure apparatus adapted to measure the vapour pressure of only the volatile constituents of the solution present. The extent of the association of TFA, the only volatile constituent in solution, in our case, was determined as a function of the measured total vapour pressure of each added increment of TFA. We had to investigate the self-association of TFA to use the results as a reference in the study of the effect of the presence of benzophenone, or substituted benzophenones. In the self-association study, increments of about 0.1 ml of TFA were added successively to the DPM in the evacuated apparatus and the corresponding pressures were recorded. In the hetero-association studies, increments of exactly about 0.1 ml TFA were also added successively to a solution of known molarity of each of the phenones in DPM in the evacuated apparatus. This was repeated for 2 concentrations of each of the phenones, which were namely 0.05 and 0.1 molar. The corresponding pressures were recorded for each increment of TFA.

Results and Discussion

As mentioned above, the results were treated on a semi-qualitative basis. It was discussed previously^{3,4}, in the detailed calculations for the self-association of TFA, that any increment of TFA added will distribute itself into an equilibrium between liquid and vapour phases. The total pressure recorded for that increment, after correcting for the pressure of air entering with it, will be the pressure due to the vapour phase which is in equilibrium with the liquid phase. Accordingly, the less the amount of TFA in the liquid phase, in equilibrium with the vapour phase, the less the observed vapour pressure and vice versa.

This last statement was actually used as the basis for following and discussing the results of the present work. When TFA is added in increments to a solution containing one of the non-volatile solutes in DPM, each increment, f_A^t , will then be divided in solution in two parts, one tied up in the non-volatile hetero-complexes, Δf_A , and the other part free to self-associate, f_A^f , and is in equilibrium with the vapour phase, as explained above. If the same increment of TFA is added to DPM in the absence of any non-volatile solute, it will all be in equilibrium with the vapour phase. The observed vapour pressures vs the corresponding formal concentrations of TFA in the presence of each non-volatile solute were plotted on the same figure including a reference curve for TFA in the absence of any non-volatile solute. Figure 1 shows a representation of the method used for calculating

Fig. 1. Representation Figure for Calculation of Different Types of Formal Concentrations of TFA.
(i) in absence of non-volatile solutes.
(ii) in presence of non-volatile solutes.

the formal concentrations of the two different types of TFA present in solution. The amount tied up in hetero-complexes, Δf_A , can be calculated as the difference between the formal concentration of TFA in DPM at a given total pressure of TFA in the presence of dissolved non-volatile solute, f_A^t , and the formal concentration of TFA in DPM at the same pressure in the absence of such a solute, f_A^f , by following the pathway shown in Fig. 1, where

$$\Delta f_A = f_A^t - f_A^f$$

Tables 1 to 3 include experimental values of total formal concentrations of added increments of TFA,

TABLE 1—DATA FOR BENZOPHENONE SYSTEM

f_A^t	0.05 molar		0.10 molar	
	f_A^f	Δf_A	f_A^f	Δf_A (molar)
0.0135	0.0055	0.0080	0.0050	0.0085
0.0270	0.0090	0.0180	0.0080	0.0190
0.0404	0.0144	0.0260	0.0199	0.0285
0.0539	0.0195	0.0344	0.0180	0.0359
0.0670	0.0250	0.0420	0.0200	0.0470
0.0808	0.0338	0.0470	0.0260	0.0548
0.0943	0.0303	0.0550	0.0310	0.0633
0.1077	0.0470	0.0607	0.0390	0.0687
0.1212	0.0560	0.0652	0.0430	0.0782
0.1346	0.0656	0.0690	0.0486	0.0860
0.1480	0.0720	0.0760	0.0530	0.0950
0.1615	0.0815	0.0800	0.0610	0.1005
0.1750	0.0905	0.0845	0.0660	0.1090

TABLE 2—DATA FOR 4-CHLOROBENZOPHENONE SYSTEM

f_A^t	0.05 molar		0.10 molar	
	f_A^f	Δf_A	f_A^f	Δf_A (molar)
0.0135	0.0075	0.0060	0.0070	0.0055
0.0270	0.0115	0.0155	0.0115	0.0155
0.0404	0.0199	0.0205	0.0165	0.0239
0.0539	0.0300	0.0239	0.0219	0.0320
0.0670	0.0370	0.0300	0.0235	0.0435
0.0808	0.0460	0.0348	0.0273	0.0435
0.0943	0.0560	0.0383	0.0435	0.0508
0.1077	0.0665	0.0412	0.0485	0.0592
0.1212	0.0760	0.0452	0.0560	0.0652
0.1346	0.0876	0.0470	0.0630	0.0716
0.1480	0.0980	0.0500	0.0710	0.0770
0.1615	0.1085	0.0530	0.0795	0.0820
0.1750	0.1205	0.0545	0.0865	0.0885

TABLE 3—DATA FOR 4-BROMOBENZOPHENONE SYSTEM

f_A^t	0.05 molar		0.10 molar	
	f_A^f	Δf_A	f_A^f	Δf_A (molar)
0.0135	0.0080	0.0055	0.0080	0.0055
0.0270	0.0140	0.0130	0.0115	0.0155
0.0404	0.0210	0.0194	0.0170	0.0234
0.0539	0.0280	0.0259	0.0220	0.0319
0.0670	0.0365	0.0305	0.0270	0.0400
0.0808	0.0465	0.0343	0.0320	0.0488
0.0943	0.0553	0.0390	0.0390	0.0553
0.1077	0.0640	0.0437	0.0440	0.0637
0.1212	0.0752	0.0460	0.0515	0.0697
0.1346	0.0836	0.0510	0.0596	0.0750
0.1480	0.0920	0.0560	0.0650	0.0830
0.1615	0.1015	0.0600	0.0730	0.0885
0.1750	0.1100	0.0650	0.0800	0.0950

f_A^t , together with the values of f_A^f and Δf_A calculated from individual figures for each concentration of each of the non-volatile solutes, as explained above. Figures 2 and 3 show comparative curves for total pressures vs formal concentrations

Fig. 2. Variation of Total Pressure with Formal Concentration of TFA in presence of (i) 0.0 M non-volatile solute (ii) 0.05 M 4-chlorobenzophenone (iii) 0.05 M 4-bromobenzophenone (iv) 0.05 M benzophenone

Fig. 3. Variation of Total Pressure with Formal Concentration of TFA in presence of (i) 0.0 M non-volatile solute (ii) 0.1 M 4-chlorobenzophenone (iii) 0.1 M 4-bromobenzophenone (iv) 0.1 M benzophenone

of TFA in the presence of each concentration of all the non-volatile solutes.

It is obvious from the tables that the presence of either substituent in the benzophenone molecule, appreciably hinders the extent of the hetero-hydrogen bonding of the latter with TFA. This is clear from the observed decrease in values of Δf_A and corresponding increase in values of f_A^t , when using either 4-chlorobenzophenone or 4-bromobenzophenone, as compared to corresponding values using the same formal concentration, f_A^t , of TFA in the presence of unsubstituted benzophenone. This means that either substituted group, when present in the indicated position in benzophenone decreases the potency of the lone pairs of electrons on the carbonyl-oxygen, hence, hindering the basic power of this oxygen atom to hydrogen bond to the acidic proton of TFA. This result can be explained on the basis of the different effects functioning in the presence of either substituent. Both the chloro and the bromo substituents, in this case, will show a (-I) inductive effect and a (+R) resonance effect. The carbonyl group of benzophenone itself shows a conjugative effect :

All these effects are shown together in the above representation. The (-I) inductive effect, which leads to withdrawal of electron density in the direction of the substituted group, will result in a decrease of the electron density on the carbonyl-oxygen, and accordingly a decrease in the potency of its lone pairs to hydrogen bond. On the other hand, the (+R) resonance effect, involving one of the lone pairs of the halo group in conjugation with the π electrons of the phenyl group next to it, and the conjugative effect of the carbonyl group, will both lead to an increase of the electron density on the carbonyl-oxygen, thus increasing its power for

hydrogen bonding. The fact that the extent of hetero-hydrogen bonding does decrease in presence of either substituted halo group indicates that the (-I) effect, in this case, is more powerful than the combined (+R) effect and the conjugative effect.

In comparing the overall effects of the chloro and bromo groups, it can be seen from Figures 2 and 3 that the chloro group decreases the extent of hetero-association of benzophenone with TFA, more than does the bromo group. This can be attributed mainly, to the fact that the (-I) effect of the chloro group is stronger than that of the bromo group; and also to the fact that the (+R) effect of the bromo group is stronger than that of the chloro group. Both these effects will lead to a larger decrease in the potency of the lone pairs of electrons

on the carbonyl-oxygen, in the case of the chloro group more than the bromo group, hence, less hetero-hydrogen bonding in the former.

References

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